

Herb-drug Interaction using the seed extract of *Hunteria umbellata* and Metronidazole in Plasma of Rabbit

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Abstract

Herbal medicines contain multiple bioactive constituents which are capable of interacting with various bio-molecular targets and therefore can interfere with the pharmacokinetics of most orthodox medicine. This work studies the pharmacokinetic profile of metronidazole administered concomitantly with *Hunteria umbellata* using rabbits. Single oral dose of metronidazole was administered to the rabbits (5.0 mg/kg) after which 2 mL of blood samples were serially withdrawn at 0, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 4.0, 8.0, 12.0 and 24 h. After a washout period of 14 days, the aqueous extract of *Hunteria umbellata* (50 mg/ml) was co-administered with metronidazole (5mg/kg) as a single oral dose. Thereafter, blood samples (2ml) were withdrawn at time interval indicated in the first phase. The samples were analyzed using a validated UV spectrophotometric assay method. The following pharmacokinetic parameters were obtained: for metronidazole only were C_{max} (4.858 μgml^{-1}), T_{max} (2.0 h), $T_{1/2}$ (3.111 h), K_a (1.647 h^{-1}), $AUC_{0-\infty}$ (40.710 $\mu\text{gml}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$), V_d (0.551 mlKg^{-1}), Cl (0.123 ml h^{-1}) and K_{el} (0.223 h^{-1}) while the pharmacokinetic parameters after co-administration are C_{max} (4.658 h), T_{max} (2.0 h), $T_{1/2}$ (2.560 h), K_a (1.850 h^{-1}), $AUC_{0-\infty}$ (28.842 $\mu\text{gml}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$), V_d (0.693 mlKg^{-1}), Cl (0.138 ml h^{-1}) and K_{el} (0.223 h^{-1}). The following parameters: AUC_{0-24} , $AUC_{0-\infty}$, K_{el} , $T_{e1/2}$ and Cl of metronidazole were significantly decreased when administered concurrently with the extract, there was no statistical difference ($p < 0.05$) in the K_a , $T_{1/2}$, C_{max} and T_{max} of metronidazole when administered alone or co-administration with *H. umbellata*. There is therefore need for proper counseling of patients on the concomitant use of metronidazole with aqueous extract of *Hunteria umbellata* seed.

Keyword: herb-drug interaction, *Hunteria umbellata*, metronidazole, Pharmacokinetics

Introduction:

The use of herbal medicine is widely practiced and accepted in most developing countries like Nigeria where most of the rural populace are poor and without access to good health care facilities (Oreagba *et al.*, 2011). This has resulted in increasing dependence on herbal medicine which is believed to be affordable, natural and therefore with less toxicity (Osemene *et al.*, 2011; Ameade *et al.*, 2018). Herbs have been used in many chronic illnesses (e.g. diabetes mellitus, ulcers, cardiovascular diseases, cancers and depression) because

of their multiple active components (e.g. alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, tannins, saponins and cardiac glycosides) and are therefore beneficial especially in such diseases with many pathological pathways (Liu *et al.*, 2015). The concomitant use of herbal medicine and prescription drugs for desired therapeutic benefit in treating diseases have oftentimes resulted in herb-drug pharmacokinetic interactions (Choi *et al.*, 2011). These interactions are of safety concern especially for drugs with narrow therapeutic index (e.g. Digoxin, Phenytoin and Warfarin etc.) and for chronic illnesses (such as cancer) which involves long-term

use of drugs (Yang *et al.*, 2014). These interactions are of special clinical significance because it could alter the pharmacokinetic parameters of the drug used concomitantly with the herb (Tarirai *et al.*, 2010; Meng and Liu, 2014). The process of drug absorption at the site of absorption into the circulatory system can be altered due to modulation of efflux and uptake transporters, complex formation, changes in gastrointestinal motility or the fluids physiological pH (Rosenkranz *et al.*, 2012). While the effect on the drug biotransformation could be due to either inhibition or induction of Cytochrome P450 metabolizing enzymes (Zhou *et al.*, 2003). These factors not only alter the bioavailability and plasma clearance of the administered therapeutic drug but also affect their effectiveness and toxicity. Some of the pharmacokinetic parameters which may be altered as a result of herb-drug interaction include: the area under the curve (AUC), the maximum plasma concentration (C_{max}), time to reach the maximum plasma concentration (T_{max}), elimination half-life and clearance etc.

In developing nations, the populace often get involved in self-medication with common drugs such as analgesic, antimicrobial, haematinics among others. Among the antimicrobial agents, metronidazole is readily available, and due the level of hygiene and the eating habit of the populace, gastrointestinal problems regularly occurred. Metronidazole is a synthetic antiprotozoal drug. It is effective against obligate anaerobic bacteria such as *Protococcus*, *Peptostreptococcus*, *Clostridium bacteroides*, and *Fusobacterium*. It is also active against few non-spores forming gram-positive organisms. Metronidazole is highly

effective against anaerobic protozoa infections including *Trichomonas vaginalis*, *Entamoeba histolytical*, *Giardia lamblia* and *Balantidium coli*. Metronidazole is the drug of choice for amoebiasis and Trichomonadic urethritis in men, lambliaosis, amoebic dysentery and other sensitive anaerobic infection (Vardanyan and Hruby, 2006; Andrews *et al.*, 2014)

2- Methyl -5- nitroimidazol-1-ethanol

The plant *Hunteria umbellata* (K. Shum) is a tropical rain forest tree which belongs to the family Apocynaceae, is widely used in traditional medicine as an antiobesity, antihyperlipidaemia, antihyperglycemia, infertility, aphrodisiac, stomachache and ulcers (Ajiboye *et al.*, 2017; Adeneye *et al.*, 2019). It is known by names such as “Demouain” (French), “Madaci” (Hausa), “Mkpokiri” (Igbo) and “Abere” (Yoruba) (Adejuwon *et al.*, 2011; Adeneye *et al.*, 2011). Some herbal medicines are known to induce CYP3A4; an enzyme which is normally responsible for the oxidative metabolism of most drugs. It is therefore important to investigate the potential outcome of most herbal-drug interactions so as to avoid their adverse effects. This effort will encourage rational and safe use of herbal medicine and therapeutic drugs as there have been an increase in their co-administration especially among the elderly patients due to the presence of two or more co-existing health challenge. To further this knowledge, we undertook this study on the pharmacokinetic interaction between the plant *Hunteria umbellata* and

the drug metronidazole using animal model.

Materials and Methods

Collection of Plant materials and authentication

Fresh mature pods of the *Hunteria umbellata* plant were collected from the deciduous forest of Offa (Kwara state, Nigeria), in April, 2018. Plant authentication was done by Mr. Suleiman, (Department of Pharmacognosy & Phytotherapy, University of Port-Harcourt) and the Voucher specimen deposited in Forest Research Institute of Nigeria, (FRIN) Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria with the reference no. FHI 109457, allotted.

Experimental animals

Four healthy white male New Zealand rabbits weighing between 1.5 -1.7 kg and aged between 4 - 6 months were purchased from the University of Port Harcourt animal house were used for the study. They were acclimatized in an environmentally controlled room (temperature about 22 °C, photo period of 12 h light and 12 h darkness with relative humidity of 60 %) for two weeks prior to the study. Prescribed feed and water were provided *ad libitum* during the period. The guideline of the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee was observed throughout the study.

The reagents used in the course of the research work were of analytical grade and these include; methanol (Guangzhou Jinhua Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd., China), sulphuric acid (Sigma Aldrich, Germany), sodium hydroxide (Sigma Aldrich, Germany), hydrochloric acid (Sigma Aldrich, Germany), Molisch's reagent, ferric chloride, chloroform, Pure sample of metronidazole, Normal saline

(Juhel Pharma, Nigeria), Water bath (HH6 Techmel and Techmel, USA) UV/Visible spectrophotometer (Techmel and Techmel, USA); Sample bottles (Skytec medical, Nigeria); Lithium heparinized sample bottle (Skytec instruments); Vortex mixer (XH-B Vortex, SearchTech China).

Methods

Extraction of Plant Materials

The de-coated seeds of *H. umbellata* were gently washed with distilled water, dried and then grinded to a coarse powder using domestic blender. A kilogram of coarsely powdered seeds of *H. umbellata* was intermittently shaken and exhaustively extracted with distilled water (1:10) for a period of 72 hours. Thereafter, the marc obtained was oven dried at 100°C. The filtrate was concentrated using rotary evaporator before it was freeze dried. The extract obtained was stored in a moisture tight clean vessel and kept in a refrigerator (4°C).

Phytochemical screening of the aqueous seed extract was carried out according to the standard methods (Trease and Evans, 2009).

In- vivo Pharmacokinetic Study

The study was a simple cross-over design comprising of phase 1 and phase 2 sections with a washout period of 2 weeks in-between. All the animals (rabbits) were made to fast overnight and remained fasted until 4 h after the drug intake. Water was given *ad libitum* during the study. In the Phase 1 of the study, the animals, were divided into: Group I; the control group animals received only water (2 ml/kg)), while the Group II animals were orally administered metronidazole (5 mg/kg) by gavage. In the phase 2: the Group I

animals were given water (2 ml/kg) while Group II animals were administered *H. umbellata* extract (50 mg/kg) by gavage every 24 h for 72 h and immediately after the last dose, 5 mg/kg metronidazole was administered. Blood samples, (2.0 mL) were collected from the ear lobe vein of the rabbits at the following time intervals: 0.0, 1.0, 2.0, 4.0, 8.0, 12.0 and 24.0 h *via* a modified cannula and transferred into a heparinized tube in both phases, centrifuged immediately at 3,500 rpm for 10 minutes and the plasma obtained were stored at -4°C until analysis.

Extraction of metronidazole from plasma

The extraction of metronidazole from the blood samples was carried out using the Ofoefule *et al.* method: Briefly: Blood samples (0.5 mL) were withdrawn from the ear lobe vein of the rabbit using a modified needle cannula syringes into a heparinized tube. This was mixed with 5 mL of 0.05M H₂SO₄ in methanol, vortex mixed and centrifuged for 10 min at 3000 rpm. The supernatant layer containing metronidazole was allowed to evaporate on water bath to a final volume of 1.0 ml and analyzed using a UV/ Visible spectrophotometer at λ_{\max} of 277 nm for metronidazole.

Preparation of Standard Solution of Metronidazole

To prepare the stock solution (100 µg/ml), 50 mg of pure metronidazole powder was accurately weighed and dissolve in 300 ml of 0.05M H₂SO₄ in methanol and the solution made to mark in a 500 ml volumetric flask. Then, 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 ml aliquot of the stock solution were separately made up to 100 ml with 0.05M

H₂SO₄ in methanol to prepare 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 µg/ml solutions respectively.

Determination of λ_{\max} and calibration curve

A milliliter of the stock solution (100 µg/ml) was diluted to 10 ml with 0.05M H₂SO₄ in methanol to obtain a 10 µg/ml solution. The absorbance of resulting solution was scanned in the UV spectrometer in the range 200 – 400 nm. The maximum absorbance value was found at a wavelength of 277 nm (λ_{\max}). The absorbance values of the different standard solutions prepared were determined at this wavelength in order to prepare the calibration curve.

Pharmacokinetic Data Analysis

The plot of plasma concentration (C) against time (t) of metronidazole alone and after co-administration with the *H. umbellata* extract was carried out using PK solver (version 2) software. The data were analyzed to obtain the pharmacokinetic parameters such as peak plasma concentration (C_{max}), time to peak plasma concentration (T_{max}), elimination rate constant (Kel), elimination half-life (T_{e1/2}); apparent volume of distribution (V_d); area under the plasma concentration–time curve (AUC) and drug clearance (Cl) were determined using non-compartmental analyses. The absorption rate constant was calculated by logarithmic linear regression of the plasma concentration–time curve. The absorption half-life was calculated as 0.693 divided by the elimination constant. The AUC to the final measurable sample was determined using the trapezoidal rule and extrapolated to infinity with the final plasma concentration being divided by the elimination constant, calculated from the

apparently linear portion of the log plasma concentration–time curve.

Statistical analysis

The results from independent experiments were analyzed statistically using Microsoft Excel (Student's t-test) and Graph pad Prism 6 software for windows (Graph pad software, San Diego CA www.graphpad.com). The data obtained were expressed as mean \pm SD. The differences between mean values were analyzed for significance using one way analysis of variance (ANOVA). $p < 0.05$

were considered to be statistically significant.

Results

The crude aqueous extract of *H. umbellata* was orange colored, which changed to chocolate brown after freeze drying. The percentage yield of the plant extract is 24.36%.

Phytochemical analysis

The phytochemical screening of the aqueous seed extract of *H. umbellata* revealed the presence of the following phytochemical compounds: saponins, alkaloids, flavonoid, anthraquinones, tannins, and cardiac glycoside (Table 1).

Table 1. The phytochemical screening of the aqueous seed extract of *H. umbellata*

Test	Observation	Inferences
Saponins		
Frothing test	Persistent frothing	Saponins present
Alkaloids		
Mayer's test	Cream precipitate	Alkaloids present
Dragendorff's test	Red precipitate present	
Hager's test	Yellow precipitate present	
Flavonoids		
Shinoda's reduction test	Orange colouration	Flavonoid present
Anthraquinones		
Borntrager's test	Violet coloration in ammonia phase	Anthraquinones present
Tannins		
Ferric chloride	A blue black colouration	Tannins present
Cardiac glycosides		
Lieberman test	A pink colouration	Triterpenoid nucleus
Burchard's test	A reddish brown colouration at the interface	Steroidal nucleus present
Salkowski's test	A reddish brown colouration	Unsaturated lactone ring

***In vivo* Pharmacokinetic Study**

The pharmacokinetic parameters of metronidazole when administered alone and after co-administration with *H. umbellata* were calculated using the non-compartmental model with PK solver

(version 2) software and the result is as shown in Table 2. The graph of mean plasma concentration –time curves (AUC) of metronidazole when administered alone and after co-administration with *H. umbellata* are shown in Figure 2.

Table 2: Pharmacokinetic parameters of metronidazole alone and after co-administration of metronidazole and *Hunteria umbellata* extract.

Pharmacokinetic parameter	Mean values	
	Metronidazole	Metronidazole + <i>H. umbellata</i> extract
K_{el} (h^{-1})	0.223	0.350
$T_{1/2}$ (h)	3.111	3.771
K_a (h^{-1})	1.647	1.850
$T_{a1/2}$ (h)	0.421	0.385
T_{max} (h)	2.000 ± 0.002	2.000 ± 0.001
C_{max} ($\mu g/ml$)	4.858 ± 0.005	4.658 ± 0.004
T_{lag} (h)	0	0
C_{last_obs}/C_{max}	0.015	0.004
AUC _{0-24h} ($\mu g/ml \cdot h$)	40.382	28.763
AUC _{0-inf_obs} ($\mu g/ml \cdot h$)	40.710	28.842
AUMC _{0-inf_obs} ($\mu g/ml \cdot h^2$)	277.778	152.475
MRT _{0-inf_obs} (h)	6.823	5.287
V_{d_obs} (ml/kg)	0.551	0.693
Cl_{obs} (ml/kg* h)	0.123	0.253

AUC: Area under the curve, T_{max} : time taken by the drug to reach the maximum concentration, C_{max} : maximum concentration of the drug, $T_{1/2}$: half-life (the period of time required for the concentration of drug in the body to be reduced by one=half), CL: Clearance (the estimate of the plasma cleared by the body per unit time: MRT: mean residence time of the drug, V_d : volume of distribution (the volume of plasma that would be necessary to account for the total amount of drug in the animal)

Determination of λ_{max} and calibration curve

The calibration curve for the determination of metronidazole (Figure 1.0) in the plasma was obtained plotting the plasma concentration against time, using UV-Visible spectrophotometer which shows linearity and sensitivity between 0 - 10 $\mu g/ml$.

Figure 1.0: Calibration curve of metronidazole in 0.05M H₂SO₄ in methanol solution

Figure 2. Plasma concentration- time curve of metronidazole and after co-administration with extract *H. umbellata*

Discussion

The use of herbal medicine as complementary medicine for most diseases has become a worldwide practice and because herbs are known to interact with some enzymes responsible for drug metabolism (CYP3A4) thereby leading to both safety issues and treatment failures. This has led to the continued research on interactions between herbs and orthodox medicine (Zhou *et al.*, 2007). From our study the phytochemical screening of the plant *H. umbellata* reveals the presence of an alkaloids, anthraquinones, cardiac

glycosides, flavonoids, saponins and tannins, which could be responsible for the plants pharmacological actions. The metronidazole absorption rate when administered alone compared to when it was administered concomitantly with *H. umbellata* shows a slight insignificant increase from 1.647 h⁻¹ to 1.850 h⁻¹. The time taken for half of the singly administered metronidazole dose to be absorbed and after its co-administration with *H. umbellata* was significantly different ($p > 0.05$): 0.421 h and 0.347 h respectively. The implication of the above

findings is that *H. umbellata* does not significantly interfere with the oral absorption of metronidazole. The time taken to achieve the maximum plasma concentration of metronidazole when singly administered and when administered concomitantly with *H. umbellata* were the same (2 h), although their peak plasma concentration differs but not significantly ($p > 0.05$): metronidazole alone is 4.858 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ while metronidazole with *H. umbellata* is 4.658 $\mu\text{g/ml}$., the above findings is in agreement with the findings of Zhou *et al.*, (2007) However, there was a significant difference in the area under the curve of plasma drug concentration versus time curve (Figure 2) and the area under the first moment curve (AUMC₀₋₂₄) which is a reflection of the body's exposure to the drug. The AUC and AUMC values when metronidazole was administered alone were 40.380 and 277.778 $\mu\text{g/ml/h}$ respectively while the values when metronidazole was co-administered with *H. umbellata* were 28.841 and 152.475 $\mu\text{g/ml/h}$ respectively. The above data indicates that *H. umbellata* significantly reduced the amount of drug that reaches the rats' bloodstream in a given period of time after a dose is given and also reduces quantitatively the area under the curve formed by time and the product of concentration and time. This is in tandem with the value of mean residence time (MRT) obtained in this study. The mean residence time (MRT) for metronidazole and *H. umbellata* when concomitantly administered (5.287 h) was lower than when metronidazole was administered alone (6.823 h). This could be supported by the result of the mean residence time (MRT) and volume of distribution (V_d) of 6.819 h and 0.549 mL/kg respectively for metronidazole

alone while the values for co-administration with *H. umbellata* were 6.287 h and 0.693 mL/kg respectively. This implies that metronidazole is more available in the tissues when administered concomitantly with *H. umbellata* than when administered alone. This could probably account for two compartmental model observed in this study (Figure 2). The elimination rate of metronidazole co-administered with *H. umbellata* (0.351 h^{-1}) was significantly higher than that of metronidazole administered alone (0.224 h^{-1}). Therefore it takes less time to eliminate metronidazole from the systemic circulation when it is administered concomitantly with the herb than when it was administered alone. The parameter which relate the amount of drug in the body to the concentration of drug in the plasma (V_d) is higher when metronidazole was administered concomitantly with *H. umbellata* (0.693 mL/kg) than when administered alone (0.551 mL/kg). This implies that *H. umbellata* either increases the lipid solubility of metronidazole through the surfactant activity of the saponins possessed by *H. umbellata* (Liao *et al.*, 2021; Rai *et al.*, 2021), increase in the tissue binding ability of metronidazole through the tissue shrinking activity of tannin possessed by *H. umbellata* (Ashok and Upadhyaya, 2012) or an increase in metronidazole plasma protein binding (Sanvordeker *et al.*, 1975). The limitation of this study include the number of rabbits, the inter-specie variation which may make interpolation to human difficult, though the study established a relationship between *H. umbellata* and metronidazole, but the study was unable to establish the mechanism of the interaction.

This study revealed that *H. umbellata* has significant effect on the amount of

metronidazole absorbed, the mean residence time, and the rate at which it is eliminated. Therefore, co-administration of *H. umbellata* and metronidazole should not be encourage rather patients should be encouraged to reveal their usage of herbal medicine together with orthodox medicine to prevent any advent of toxicities. Herb-drug interaction can have a lethal effect especially where poly-pharmacy is a common practice.

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Conflict-of-Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Authors' Declaration

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